

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF AFGHANISTAN'S POLITICAL SYSTEM:
FROM KINGDOM TO TALIBAN RULE**

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the stages of formation and development of the Afghan political system, from the monarchy to the Taliban's rise to power. The article systematically covers the transition from monarchy to the Republic, state governance during the socialist regime, political chaos during the civil war, the system used by the United States for the Afghan people, and the Taliban government's efforts to gain power and rise to power.

The first and second governments of the Taliban and the stages of development of institutions with US participation are described.

Key words: Evolution, modernization, intervention, gender equality, monarchy, democracy, АКР

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируются этапы становления и развития политической системы Афганистана от монархии до прихода к власти Талибана. В статье системно освещаются переход от монархии к республике, государственное управление в период социалистического режима, политический хаос в период гражданской войны, система, используемая Соединенными Штатами для афганского народа, а также усилия правительства Талибана по завоеванию власти и приходу к власти.

Описываются первое и второе правительства Талибана и этапы развития институтов с участием США.

Ключевые слова: Эволюция, модернизация, вмешательство, гендерное равенство, монархия, демократия, ПСР

ENTRANCE

Today, the state of Afghanistan is considered one of the countries in the center of the world, because this state is a state with many political conflicts. In recent times, this state has been characterized by the volatility, instability of the political system, and a high degree of openness to external interference. The evolution of the political system of Afghanistan began with the monarchy and then went through such stages as republicanism, the socialist regime, the Islamic approach, the regime established under the leadership of the USA, and again the government in the form of an Islamic emirate proclaimed by the Taliban.

In this state, depending on the form of government, both political institutions and forms of government changed. In particular, the coming to power of the Taliban government in 2021 raised a number of questions regarding diplomatic relations, gender equality, and democratic changes.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The formation of the political system of Afghanistan dates back to the era of the Durrani Empire, founded in the middle of the 18th century by Ahmad Shah Durrani. From the foundation of the Durrani Empire, the administration of Afghanistan was based on traditional tribal structures and Islamic Sharia. Political decisions were made through tribal chiefs and the council system. During the reign of Ahmad Shah Durrani, the political system of the Afghan people developed, and they began to form as a single state.

After 1801, that is, after dissatisfaction with Zamanshah's policy, an uprising occurred and Zamanshah was overthrown. After this, there was political fragmentation in Afghanistan until the arrival of Dost Mohammad, the founder of the Barakzai dynasty. During the time of the Barakzai dynasty, the Anglo-Afghan War also took place and was difficult for the Afghans.¹ During the First and Second Anglo-Afghan Wars, the productive forces weakened considerably. Agriculture, crafts, and trade fell significantly behind. Many cities and villages were destroyed and burned. Due to the extermination of their inhabitants, many tribes were weakened.

¹ M. Boboxo'jayev, *A New History of Afghanistan (1747-1918), TASHKENT-1997* P.15

Subsequently, a constitutional monarchy was introduced, and modernization processes began. After Amanullah Khan's accession to the throne in 1926, a number of political institutions such as women's rights, education, and others began to take shape.

In 1973, Mohammad Daoud Khan seized the throne through a coup and proclaimed the Republic of Afghanistan. However, this system, not based on political pluralism, did not last long. However, Muhammad Davud Khan abolished the monarchy and implemented many reforms, as the monarchy hindered any reforms.

In August 1973, Mohammad Daoud announced his program of action on the country's domestic and foreign policy, known as the "Appeal to the People." The head of state, who sharply criticized the previous regime, put forward political, economic, and social reforms of society in accordance with the will of the Afghan people. Muhammad Davud also began to create the legal basis for his rule and introduced a new constitution. In 1978, as a result of a coup d'état, he was killed by revolutionaries. Thus, a constitutional monarchy was established in Afghanistan.²

After the state fell into the hands of the revolutionaries, Soviet troops invaded Afghanistan in 1979 and remained there for 10 years. In 1989, they withdrew their troops, but this intensified political fragmentation in the country and led to the disruption of the political system.

In 1990, the "Vatan" party was formed in Kabul instead of the NDPU. This party has announced its new political program and begun widespread public work." The "Vatan" party began to promote such ideas as democratic reforms in the country, the creation of laws based on the will of the people, and the rejection of socialism in favor of Islam.³ From monarchy to republic, the Afghan people went through such stages, and in 1996, with a completely new system, the Taliban government seized power and declared the country the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan.

A strict religious administration based on Sharia law was introduced. The arrival of the Taliban was very difficult for the people, as they imposed very strong and strict restrictions on the population. Schools were closed for women, their work was

² History of Afghanistan., recommended by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan as a textbook for students., History of Afghanistan textbook.-T.: "Barkamol fayz media," 2018. - 344 p.

³ Anthony, A. The Ephemeral Elite. The Failure of Socialist Afghanistan Political Parties and Restructuring Order in Socialist Afghanistan. New York, 1988 - P.21.

prohibited, and their freedom was restricted. During this period, Afghanistan fell into international isolation, and the political system was based on religious ideology.

After the US intervention in 2001, a new political system was created in Afghanistan. Thus, in October 2001, as a result of the anti-terrorist operation carried out by the US-led anti-terrorist coalition in Afghanistan, the Taliban government was dismantled, and a new government representing the interests of the majority was formed.⁴ Hamid Karzai was appointed head of this government. During this period, a number of benefits were created for the Afghan people, presidential administration, parliamentary elections, and most importantly, gender equality were ensured.

In 2021, after the withdrawal of US troops from the country, the country again fell into the hands of the Taliban and restored the "Islamic Emirate." To this day, this Taliban movement has caused discontent in the international community and remains far from institutional legitimacy due to the religious-ideological basis of the political system.

CONCLUSION

Although the political system of Afghanistan is in constant evolution, no form has been firmly established and not supported by the people. This state has a long history and was governed by systems with different directions at each stage of its existence. From monarchy to democracy, every experiment failed due to external factors and a lack of political culture.

The current government, under the guise of religion, is controlling the people, which causes discontent not only among the people, but also among international organizations and neighboring countries.

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